

Mathematical Analysis of a Magnetic and Conducting Fluid Flow through Blood Vessel Along with an Inclination and Chemical Reaction

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Abstract:

This research paper presents a theoretical investigation of the combined effects of chemical reaction and heat source on blood flow via a tapered vessel in the presence of angle of inclination and magnetohydrodynamics. The continuity, momentum and concentration equations are used to model the proposed problem in terms of nonlinear partial differential equations. These equations along with the initial and boundary conditions is made dimensionless and then solved numerically using power series method. The computational results are presented graphically for the blood velocity, temperature, and concentration distributions in terms of the

different parameter values used in this analysis. The study shows that the existence of the controlling parameters significantly impacts the characteristics of the flow.

Keywords: *Chemical reaction, Conducting Fluid, Magnetic field, angle of inclination, blood flow, Blood vessel, Mathematical Analysis.*

Introduction

For many reasons, blood flow via vessels is significant. It has an impact on the stability of vessels, with factors influencing the critical buckling pressure of vessels including blood flow velocity, hematocrit, and stiffness of surrounding tissues (Mark & Alexander, 2011). In order for immune cells to operate properly and for oxygen and nutrients to be delivered, red and white blood cells must circulate efficiently via microcirculation (Sun & Munn, 2008). The non-Newtonian characteristics of blood make it challenging to understand the physical mechanisms by which individual blood cells contribute to its bulk flow characteristics. To

explore the impact of individual cells on macroscopic blood rheology, a Lattice-Boltzmann model, however, has been created. This model makes it possible to predict the characteristics of blood flow in any vessel shape and with any blood composition. (Park Jong, 2020). Ultrasonic sensor modules can also be used to assess blood flow, giving information about blood vessel health, and indicating the existence or absence of illnesses. Additionally, assessing blood flow rates and analyzing the performance based on these readings are necessary to ascertain the effectiveness of a vessel, such as a hemodialysis fistula (Tanaka, Ohta, & Hagiwara, 2007).

There are many applications for blood flow through vessels in the areas of medicine and biological research. Virtual surgery and detection of vascular disorders are two applications where it is essential to couple the blood flow and vessel wall in real-time (Zhang, Sun, & Chen, 2020). Another application is in drug distribution, where it's crucial to comprehend the blood's particle nature and red blood cells' capacity for deformation for targeted therapy. (Watanabe & Shintao, 2020). The study of modified flow conditions in the vascular system and their significance in arterial disorders uses computational modeling of blood flow (Park Jong, 2020). Additionally, tools and techniques for measuring blood flow and keeping an eye on blood vessel health have been developed, which can assist with disease prediction and vascular health optimization (Park, Shin, & Hyung Ham, 2020). The movement of fluids through a system of tubes is analogous to the flow of blood through vessels. It is essential to understand the forces acting on bends and bifurcations in blood veins, as well as whether the flow is laminar or turbulent, similar to how water moves through pipes. Because blood has non-Newtonian qualities, it behaves differently in tubes than water does (Nubar, 1966). Particles, notably red blood cells, and the presence of pressure gradients, artery diameters, and other variables all influence blood flow. Blood flow studies can help us understand how atherosclerotic plaques form and how diseases like myocardial infarction and weak cerebral circulation are brought on (Ryu Geun, et al., 2018). Blood flow in vessels is measured and found using a number of techniques, such as Doppler spectrum analysis. For diagnostic reasons, blood pressure waveforms of various types are replicated in blood vessel simulators.

A number of factors, such as heat source, magnetic field, chemical reaction, and angle of inclination, can affect how blood flows through a vessel. In numerous academic studies, these factors have been addressed. Isah et al. (2023) examined the effects of a heat source and a chemical reaction on the electro-magnetohydrodynamic (EMHD) blood flow through bifurcated arteries with an external

slanted magnetic field for the treatment of malignancies. Blood functioning as a heat sink in a bifurcated channel during thermal ablation therapy has been studied by Das and Mahapatra (2022). This study evaluated the heat sink effect during hyperthermia treatment in patients with HVS blood disease and patients with normal tumors and discovered that patients with hyper viscosity syndrome have a smaller heat sink effect compared to patients with normal tumors. In order to study the effects of a heat source and chemical reaction on MHD blood flow in permeable bifurcated arteries with an angled magnetic field, specifically with regard to the treatment of carotid body tumors, Kumar et al. (2021) developed a mathematical model. The biochemical reactions between blood species and the supplied reactants (drugs), which can alter blood flow rates and cause tumor destruction, are examined in this study to determine the effects of chemical reaction parameters. The impact of a heat source on MHD blood flow through bifurcated arteries has been considered by Prakash et al. (2011) The study considers the irregular Newtonian blood flow through the arteries and discovers that heat source and magnetic field alter the flow patterns and raise blood temperature. Bunonyo and Ebiwareme (2023) investigated how a heat source affected blood flow in a gradient-tapered vessel whilst being affected by a gradient magnetic field. Omamoke et al. (2020) have researched on the effects of chemical reaction, heat source, and thermal radiation on irregular blood flow via a plate channel with an angled magnetic field in a porous media.

An analytical study of MHD blood flow in a porous inclined stenotic artery under the influence of an inclined magnetic field was carried out by Srivastava (2014). The effects of arterial wall characteristics on Newtonian fluid flow via an inclined tapering porous artery with slight axially non-symmetric stenosis under the influence of an external inclined magnetic field are taken into consideration in this work. As reported by Zigta (2017), blood flow in a stretching permeable channel under the effect of heat radiation, chemical reaction, and a time-dependent magnetic field intensity has been

theoretically analysed. According to the simulated results, permeability and unsteadiness parameter increases result in an increase in blood flow velocity. As the Prandtl number and Hartmann number rise, the blood's temperature rises at the vessel wall. As the time-dependent chemical reaction parameter and Schmidt number rise, the blood concentration falls. Under the effects of thermal radiation, velocity slip, and thermal slip conditions, Misra and Sinha (2013) addressed the problem of magnetohydrodynamic flow of blood in a capillary, treating the lumen as porous and the wall as permeable. The analysis considers the unsteadiness in the flow and temperature fields brought on by the stretching velocity and surface temperature's temporal dependency. Priyadarshini and David (2023) have appraised how different drugs affected blood flow's ability to transfer heat under the impact of thermal radiation and magnetic fields. The study deals with measuring the flow rate, temperature, and drug concentration of blood in a permeable stretched capillary. The study found that permeability factor improves velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles while decreasing skin friction and enhancing mass transfer and heat transfer rates, and magnetic field can control blood velocity and increase drug concentration at the boundary layer. Sharmar and Kumawat (2021) tackle the effects of temperature-dependent viscosity and thermal conductivity on MHD blood flow via a stretching surface with ohmic effect and chemical reaction. A non-tapered artery with slight stenosis that is inclined at an angle from the axis was studied mathematically by Tripathi and Sharma (2018) to determine the effects of heat and mass transfer on arterial blood flow when an applied magnetic field was present. Analysis and study of blood flow via

stenosed arteries under the influence of a magnetic field that includes a heat source has been described by Bunonyo et al. (2018). The parameter variation method, which focuses on different parameters like velocity, temperature, wall shear stress, concentration, frequency rate, and volumetric flow rate, examines the combined effects of chemical reaction and heat source on the circulation of blood in arteries with an elliptical shape has been perused by Kumar and Kumar (2022). The results of this study have potential medicinal uses, especially for the treatment of cardiovascular disorders.

To our knowledge, no studies have been conducted to investigate the issue of blood flow through a vessel while being simultaneously influenced by a heat source, magnetic field, angle of inclination, and chemical reaction. The objective of the current study is to investigate the combined effects of chemical reaction and heat source on the flow of blood via a tapered vessel when there is an angle of inclination to the fluid axis and a magnetic field. The governing boundary layer equations are converted to ordinary differential equations using non-dimensional variables, and the resulting equations are then solved using a semi-analytical method in terms of the important key parameters of interest, such as the Froude number, magnetic field, chemical reaction parameter, angle of inclination, heat source parameter, Reynold number, Grashof number, Schmidt number, Prandtl number, and modified Grashof number. Numerical results are presented for the flow velocity, temperature, and concentration. The main outcomes of this study are anticipated to be relevant and implementable in the healthcare industry.

Materials and Methods

Mathematical Formulation

The equations describing the steady flow of blood through a cylindrical artery inclined at an angle α following Srivastava (2014) and Bunonyo and Ebiwareme (2023) is given as:

$$\rho \bar{F} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial z^*} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u^*}{\partial r^{*2}} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial r^*} \right) - \frac{\mu u^*}{k^*} + \bar{J} \times \bar{B} \quad (1)$$

According to Darcy's law, the blood velocity is:

$$u^* = -\frac{k^*}{\mu} \frac{\partial P^*}{\partial z^*} \quad (2)$$

Following the current density and magnetic field relation, we have:

$$\bar{J} \times \bar{B} = \sigma (\bar{E} + \bar{u} \times \bar{B}) \times \bar{B} \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_T = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\rho - \rho_\infty}{T^* - T_\infty} \right) \quad (4)$$

Substituting equations (2)-(4) into equation (1), we have the momentum equation reduces to:

$$\rho g \sin \alpha = \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u^*}{\partial r^{*2}} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial r^*} \right) + \rho \beta_T (T^* - T_\infty) \cos \alpha_2 + \rho \beta_c (C^* - C_\infty) - \frac{\mu u^*}{k^*} - \sigma B_0^2 u^* \quad (5)$$

We shall introduce the energy equation with a source to investigate the effect of heat source on equation (5), according to Bunonyo and Amos (Nubar, 1966), we have:

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T^*}{\partial t^*} = k_T \left(\frac{\partial^2 T^*}{\partial r^{*2}} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial T^*}{\partial r^*} \right) + Q_0 (T^* - T_\infty) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial C^*}{\partial t^*} = k_T \left(\frac{\partial^2 C^*}{\partial r^{*2}} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial r^*} \right) - Kr (C^* - C_\infty) \quad (7)$$

Equations (5-7) are subject to the following boundary conditions:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u^* = 0, T^* = T_w, C^* = C_w & \quad \text{at } r^* = h^* \\ \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial r^*} = 0, T^* = T_\infty, C^* = C_\infty & \quad \text{at } r^* = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

To make equations (5)-(8) dimensionless, we introduce the following quantities:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} z^* &= \frac{z}{d}, r^* = \frac{r}{d_0}, h^* = \frac{h}{d_0}, v^* = \frac{bv}{\delta u}, u^* = \frac{u}{u_0}, k^* = \frac{k}{d_0^2}, P^* = \frac{Pd_0^2}{d\mu\mu_0}, t^* = \frac{vt}{d_0^2}, \\ Fr &= \frac{u_0^2}{gd_0}, M = \frac{\sigma d_0^2 B_0^2}{\mu}, Re = \frac{\rho u_0 d_0}{\mu}, \theta = \frac{T^* - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, \phi = \frac{C^* - C_\infty}{C - C_w}, Rd = \frac{Q_0 d_0^2}{\mu c_p}, \\ Gr &= \frac{d_0^2 \beta_r (T_w - T_\infty)}{\nu u_0}, Gc = \frac{d_0^2 \beta_c (C - C_w)}{\nu u_0}, Pr = \frac{\mu c_p}{k_T}, Rd_0 = \frac{Krd_0^2}{\nu}, Sc = \frac{\nu}{D_m} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Using equation (8), the momentum and energy equations (5) to (7) reduces to the form.

$$\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} - \left(\frac{1}{k} + M^2 \cos^2 \alpha_1 \right) u + \theta Gr \cos \alpha_2 + \phi Gc \quad (10)$$

$$Pr \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial r} + Rd Pr \theta \quad (11)$$

$$Sc \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + Rd_0 Sc \phi \quad (12)$$

Equations (9)-(12) are subjected to the following boundary conditions:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = 0, \theta = 1, \phi = 1 & \quad \text{at } r = h \\ \frac{du}{dr} = 0, \theta = 0, \phi = 0 & \quad \text{at } r = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

Reduction to ODE

In order to reduce equations (10)-(13) from PDE to ODE, we introduce the following perturbation equations as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u &= u_0 \\ \theta &= \theta_0 e^{\omega t} \\ \phi &= \phi_0 e^{\omega t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

Applying equation (14) in reducing equations (10)-(13), we have the following:

$$\frac{d^2 u_0}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{du_0}{dr} - \beta_1^2 u_0 + \theta_0 Gr \cos \alpha_2 + \phi_0 Gc - \frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d^2\theta_0}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\theta_0}{dr} + \beta_2^2 \theta_0 = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{d^2\phi_0}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\phi_0}{dr} + \beta_3^2 \phi_0 = 0 \quad (17)$$

The corresponding boundary conditions are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_0 = 0, \theta_0 = e^{-\omega t}, \phi_0 = e^{-\omega t} & \quad \text{at } r = h \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial r} = 0, \theta_0 = 0, \phi_0 = 0 & \quad \text{at } r = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

where $\beta_1^2 = \left(\frac{1}{k} + M^2 \cos^2 \alpha_1 \right)$, $\beta_2^2 = (Rd - \omega) Pr$, $\beta_3^2 = (Rd_0 - \omega) Sc$

Method of Solution

The reduced equations (15-17) subject to the imposed boundary condition in equation (18) are solved by implementing the series method wherein the independent variables are presented as follows:

$$\phi_0(r) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n r^{n+\alpha} \quad (19)$$

$$\theta_0(r) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n r^{n+\alpha} \quad (20)$$

$$u_0(r) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n r^{n+\alpha} \quad (21)$$

Solving equations (16) and (17) using the equations (19) and (20), we obtained the following:

$$\phi_0(r) = a_0 A_1 J_0(\beta_3 r) + B_1 a_0 \left[J_0(\beta_3 r) \log r + \frac{\beta_3^2 r^2}{4} \left(1 - \frac{6\beta_3^2 r^2}{4^3} + \frac{44\beta_3^4 r^4}{4^3 \cdot 6^3} \right) \right] \quad (22)$$

$$\theta_0(r) = a_0 A_2 J_0(\beta_2 r) + B_2 a_0 \left[J_0(\beta_2 r) \log r + \frac{\beta_2^2 r^2}{4} \left(1 - \frac{6\beta_2^2 r^2}{4^3} + \frac{44\beta_2^4 r^4}{4^3 \cdot 6^3} \right) \right] \quad (23)$$

For the solution to be bounded, then, $B_1 = 0$ and $B_2 = 0$ in equations (22) and (23), so that they are reduced to:

$$\phi_0(r) = A_1 J_0(\beta_3 r) \quad (24)$$

$$\theta_0(r) = A_2 J_0(\beta_2 r) \quad (25)$$

Solving equations (24) and (25) subject to the boundary conditions in equation (18), we have

$$\phi_0(r) = \frac{e^{-\omega t} J_0(\beta_3 r)}{J_0(\beta_3 h)} \quad (26)$$

$$\theta_0(r) = \frac{e^{-\omega t} J_0(\beta_2 r)}{J_0(\beta_2 h)} \quad (27)$$

Since the cardinal objective of this research is to investigate the contributions of the rise in temperature and the increase in the concentration on blood circulation in an incline artery in an inclined object, we substitute equations (26) and (27) into the dimensionless momentum equation (15), that is:

$$\frac{d^2 u_0}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{du_0}{dr} - \beta_1^2 u_0 = \frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha - \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{J_0(\beta_2 h)} J_0(\beta_2 r) - \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{J_0(\beta_3 h)} J_0(\beta_3 r) \quad (28)$$

The homogenous solution of equation (28) is:

$$u_{0h}(r) = A_3 I_0(\beta_1 r) \quad (29)$$

Let the particular solution of equation (28) be:

$$u_{0p}(r) = B_3 + A_4 J_0(\beta_2 r) + B_4 J_0(\beta_3 r) \quad (30)$$

Differentiating equation (30) of order 2 and substituting the result into equation (28), we have:

$$B_3 = \frac{1}{\beta_1^2} \left(-\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha \right), B_4 = \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_3 h)} \text{ and } A_4 = \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_2 h)} \quad (31)$$

Substituting equation (31) into equation (30), then the particular solution of equation (28) becomes:

$$u_{0p}(r) = \frac{1}{\beta_1^2} \left(-\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha \right) + \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_2 h)} J_0(\beta_2 r) + \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_3 h)} J_0(\beta_3 r) \quad (32)$$

Hence, the general solution to equation (28) is the sum of equations (29) and (32), that is:

$$u_0(r) = A_3 I_0(\beta_1 r) + \frac{1}{\beta_1^2} \left(-\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha \right) + \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_2 h)} J_0(\beta_2 r) + \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_3 h)} J_0(\beta_3 r) \quad (33)$$

To obtain the blood velocity at the wall of the artery, we apply the boundary condition in equation (18), which is:

$$u_0(r) = A_3 I_0(\beta_1 r) + \frac{1}{\beta_1^2} \left(-\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha \right) + \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_2 h)} J_0(\beta_2 r) + \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{\beta_1^2 J_0(\beta_3 h)} J_0(\beta_3 r) \quad (34)$$

Simplifying equation (34), we obtain:

$$u_0(r) = \frac{1}{\beta_1^2} \left(-\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha \right) \left(1 - \frac{I_0(\beta_1 r)}{I_0(\beta_1 h)} \right) + \left(\frac{J_0(\beta_2 r)}{J_0(\beta_2 h)} - \frac{I_0(\beta_1 r)}{I_0(\beta_1 h)} \right) \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{\beta_1^2} + \left(\frac{J_0(\beta_3 r)}{J_0(\beta_3 h)} - \frac{I_0(\beta_1 r)}{I_0(\beta_1 h)} \right) \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{\beta_1^2} \quad (35)$$

where $A_3 = \frac{1}{\beta_1^2 I_0(\beta_1 h)} \left(\frac{Re}{Fr} \sin \alpha - P_0 \right) - \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gr \cos \alpha_2}{\beta_1^2 I_0(\beta_1 h)} - \frac{e^{-\omega t} Gc}{\beta_1^2 I_0(\beta_1 h)}$

Results

Following the mathematical formulation and solving the models using series method of solution, where the results for temperature and concentration profiles as well as velocity profile were obtained. In this section, numerical

simulation using Wolfram Mathematica, version 12 was carried out and the data used in the simulation are derived from Bunonyo and Ebiwareme (2023) the graphical results for the temperature, concentration and velocity of the fluid profiles are achieved by varying some of the pertinent parameters. The results presented as:

Figure 1. The Effect of Reynolds Number on Blood Velocity with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 2. The Effect of Prandtl Number on the Fluid Temperature with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 3. The effect of Radiation Parameter on the Fluid Temperature with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 4. The Effect of Porosity on the Fluid Velocity with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 5. The Effect of Concentration Parameter on the Fluid Specie Concentration in the Fluid with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 6. The Effect of Schmidt Number on the Fluid Specie Concentration with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 7. The Effect of Magnetic Field on the Fluid Velocity with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 8. The Effect of Solutal Grashof Number on the Fluid Velocity with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 9. The Effect of Froude Number on the Fluid Velocity with Other Contributing Parameters

Figure 10. The Effect of Thermal Grashof Number on the Fluid Velocity with Other Contributing Parameters

Discussion

Figure 1 illustrates that the fluid velocity is maximum at the center when the Reynolds number is 0.2 units but decreases with an increase in boundary layer thickness before converging to zero when the boundary layer thickness is maximum at 0.5. However, with the increase in Reynolds number from 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8, the velocity decreases to its maximum before decreasing to zero at the peak of the boundary layer thickness. Figure 2 depicts that the temperature in the fluid increases with an increase in the Prandtl number. This result is of the view that there was a maximum temperature at the center of the vessel but gradually decreased as the vessel thickness increased from zero to 0.5. Figure 3 depicts that the fluid temperature attained a maximum for the radiation level of 0.2 units, then began to decrease with an increase in vessel thickness. In addition, the fluid temperature increases as the radiation level increases; however, they all decrease to a unitary maximum as the boundary layer thickness reaches its maximum. Figure 4 illustrates that the fluid velocity is maximum at the center of the vessel before decreasing to zero due to the inhibition of the increasing boundary layer thickness. However, the fluid velocity increases for different values of the porosity owing to the different maximum center values, but all decreases to zero at the maximum boundary layer thickness. Figure 5 illustrates a

maximum concentration at the center of the vessel for the value of the chemical reaction observed at 2 units; thereafter, the concentration decreases to the unitary maximum as the boundary layer thickness attains 0.5. Figure 6 shows a maximum concentration at the center of the vessel for the Schmidt number at 0.2 units; thereafter, the concentration decreases to the unitary maximum as the boundary layer thickness grows to 0.5. Furthermore, for different values of the Schmidt number, the specie concentration increases, as seen at the different maximum at the center of the vessel. Figure 7 showed that the fluid velocity began at its maximum at the center when the magnetic field parameter was 2 units, but the velocity decreased to zero as the boundary layer thickness was increased to 0.5. This decrease is due to the fact that when electrically conducting fluids such as blood interact with magnetic fields, they generate a retarding force called the Lorentz force. However, the various effects converged at zero velocity for the maximum boundary layer thickness. Figure 8 illustrates that the fluid velocity reached its peak at the center when the solutal Grashof number was 5 units; thereafter, the velocity decreased to zero where the thickness was 0.5. Afterwards, we observed that the fluid velocity continuously increases for any corresponding increase in solutal Grashof number and reaches its minimum at the peak of the boundary layer thickness. Figure 9 depicts that the fluid velocity attained its maximum at

the center, where the Froude number is 0.1 unit; thereafter, the velocity converged to zero as the boundary layer thickness was increased to 0.5. Furthermore, it's seen that the fluid velocity increases with an increase in the Froude number from 0.1 to 0.5 units based on the fact that there is an incremental maximum velocity at the center, and all converge to zero at a thickness of 0.5. Figure 10 depicts that the fluid velocity attained its maximum at the center when the Grashof number was 5 units; thereafter, the velocity decreased to zero as the boundary layer thickness was increased to 0.5. Furthermore, it was observed that the fluid velocity increased with an increase in Grashof number from 5 units to 20 units, and all converged to zero at a thickness of 0.5.

Conclusion

In his research, mathematical modeling of a magnetic and conducting fluid flow through a blood vessel at an inclination was formulated, and the resulting models were solved using the series method. The objective was to investigate the influence of the entering parameters on the fluid velocity, temperature, and specie concentration, respectively. In view of the objectives spelled out, we could conclude as follows:

- The fluid velocity and temperature profiles increase with an increase in Reynolds number and Prandtl number.
- The fluid temperature profile increased with an increase in heat radiation level.
- The fluid velocity increased with an increase in porosity.
- The species concentration increased due to an increase in chemical reactions.
- The species concentration increased with an increase in Schmidt number.
- The fluid velocity decreases with an increase in the magnetic field parameter.
- The solutal and thermal Grashof numbers influenced the fluid velocity to increase.

- The Froude number increase influenced the fluid velocity to increase as well.

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Appendix

$$I_0(\beta_1 r) = \left(1 + \frac{\beta_1^2 r^2}{4} + \frac{\beta_1^4 r^4}{64} + \frac{\beta_1^6 r^6}{2304} \right) \text{ and } I_0(\beta_1) = \left(1 + \frac{\beta_1^2}{4} + \frac{\beta_1^4}{64} + \frac{\beta_1^6}{2304} \right)$$
$$J_0(\beta_2 r) = \left(1 - \frac{\beta_2^2 r^2}{2^2} + \frac{\beta_2^4 r^4}{2^2 \cdot 4^2} - \frac{\beta_2^6 r^6}{2^2 \cdot 4^2 \cdot 6^2} \right) \text{ and } J_0(\beta_2) = \left(1 - \frac{\beta_2^2}{2^2} + \frac{\beta_2^4}{2^2 \cdot 4^2} - \frac{\beta_2^6}{2^2 \cdot 4^2 \cdot 6^2} \right)$$